

Semi-stable model of Belyi children's drawings

1 Introduction

Let p be a prime number different from 2, K the algebraic closure of $\mathbb{Q}_p$. Note v a valuation of K normalized by the relation $v(p) = 1$ and $\mathcal{O}_K$ the ring of integers of K . We will finally note $\mathfrak{m}_K$ the non-invertible integers of K and $k = \mathcal{O}_K/\mathfrak{m}_K$ the residue field of $\mathcal{O}_K$.

We will study in this article the coverings $\beta : \mathbb{P}_K^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{P}_K^1$ defined by $\beta(X) = X^a(1-X)^b$ where a and b are two strictly positive integers, i.e. the cover β is totally ramified at infinity and $\mathcal{B} : \mathbb{A}_K^1 = \text{Spec}(K[X]) \rightarrow \mathbb{A}_K^1 = \text{Spec}(K[T])$ is defined via $\mathcal{B}^*(T) = X^a(1-X)^b \in K[X]$. We will also recall some properties of the coverings $\beta(X) = X^n$.

In the article [1] is clarified how one can in an elementary way describe a semi-stable model of these sort of coverings which will be uniquely determined by the fact that it will be minimal among the semi-stable model separating the points of the fibers above critical values. Such a model will be called a **minimal vertices separation model**. We will apply this method to the star coverings $\beta(X) = X^n$ and the Belyi coverings $\beta(X) = X^a(1-X)^b$.

Note that in this article distances are generally considered valuatively. In this perspective, two points P and Q are declared close when $v(P-Q) > 0$, distant when $v(P-Q) < 0$ and at critical distance when $v(P-Q) = 0$.

2 First example

Let $p = 3$ and β be the covering $\beta : \mathbb{P}_K^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{P}_K^1$ totally ramified at ∞ and $\beta(X) = X^3(1-X)^4$ on the affine plane.

In $K = \mathbb{C}$, such a covering is called a children drawing because it has only 3 critical values 0, ∞ and $\lambda \neq 0$. We represent these sort of covering by pulling back the segment $(0, \lambda)$ and marking with white vertices the preimages of 0, with black vertices the preimages of λ . Here the covering $\beta(X) = X^3(1-X)^4$ has the following representation:

Now, in $K = \overline{\mathbb{Q}_3}$ we can do arithmetic on this covering by study of its reduction modulo 3. This cover has bad reduction: some of the vertices reduce on other vertices. To see this we first calculate the branch points

$$\beta'(X) = X^2(1-X)^3(3(1-X) - 4X) = X^2(1-X)^3(3-7X)$$

so they are 0, 1 and $\frac{3}{7}$ whose images are the critical values 0 and $\lambda = \frac{3^3 4^4}{7^7}$. The main tool for seeing the reduction type is Newton polygons. The Newton polygon of $\beta(X) - \lambda$ is

From this polygon we can see that there are three black vertices (pre-image of λ) which have valuation 1 hence are reduced on the white vertex $\mathcal{O} = 0$ (among these vertices there is the black ramified vertex $C = \frac{3}{7}$). To another point the Newton polygon of $\beta(1+X) - \lambda$ is

so that there are four black vertices which are reducing on the white vertex $I = 1$. This model has bad reduction too for the reason that the critical value $\lambda = \frac{3^3 4^4}{7^7}$ is reducing on the other critical value 0.

We can build a new model which separates black vertices from $\mathcal{O}$:

$$\mu(Z) = \beta(3Z)3^{-3} = Z^3(1-3Z)^4$$

In this model all the vertices are divided by 3 and the critical value is divided by 3^3 . The Newton polygon of $\mu(Z) - \frac{4^4}{7^7}$ is a sort of rotation of the first polygon:

We can glue these two models by making blow-ups which gives on the level of special fibers the following diagram:

In the model μ there is a bad reduction between the black vertices separated from O as we can see on the Newton polygon of $\mu\left(\frac{1}{7} + X\right) - \frac{4^4}{7^7}$:

The model $\psi = \mu\left(\frac{1}{7} + 3X\right) 3^{-1}$ separates this vertex from C (0 in this model):

If we turn back to the first model β (which is called the **fundamental model**) there is bad reduction between I and black vertex as we have seen. The model

$$\mu_2(Z) = \beta\left(1 + 3^{3/4}Z\right) 3^{-3}$$

separates these vertices from I :

In this model there is no bad reduction between the black vertices previously close to I , as we will see later: this is the **minimal vertices separation model**.

3 Minimal model of star coverings

In this section we are studying the star coverings $\beta(X) = X^n$. The results below are essentially already known, but we recall them because we will make use of them later. The cover defined by $\beta(X) = X^n$ corresponds to the child's star drawing of the following type:

If n is coprime to p then the reduction $\bar{\beta} : \bar{\mathbb{F}}_p \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{F}}_p$ is separable and we can then simplify the study of the reduction by the following lemma.

Lemma 1. *If $\bar{\beta}' \neq 0$ then there is no bad reduction between unramified vertices of the same (not infinite) fiber.*

Proof. If $\beta(X) - \lambda = c \prod_l (X - x_l)^{e_l}$ with λ a critical value of the cover β such that $\bar{x}_i = \bar{x}_j = \bar{x}$ then

$$\bar{\beta}(X) - \bar{\lambda} = \bar{c}(X - \bar{x})^{e_i+e_j} \prod_{l \neq i,j} (X - \bar{x}_l)^{e_l}$$

As a result,

$$\bar{\beta}'(X) = (X - \bar{x})^{e_i+e_j-1} Q(X)$$

so $\bar{x}$ is present in the derivative of $\bar{\beta}$, so it is also the reduction of a branch point of β . $\square$

Thus the only bad vertex reduction possible is on the central ramified vertex O , but the n -th roots being invertible in $\mathcal{O}_K$ then they do not reduce on O . This covering therefore has a good reduction.

If n is of type $n = p^k$ with $k \geq 1$, there is still no reduction of the vertices on the central vertex O but it is possible that there are reductions between black vertices of the corona. We will study the proximity of vertices by Newton's polygons. Thus to study the proximity of the black vertices with the black vertex $s = 1$ we will study the Newton polygon of the polynomial

$$\beta(1 + X) - 1 = (1 + X)^{p^k} - 1$$

The following lemma will often be used to study the valuations of the coefficients of this type of polynomial.

Lemme 2. For any natural number m prime to p and any natural number $j \leq p^k m$,

$$v_p \binom{p^k m}{j} = k - v_p(j)$$

This lemma can be proved easily by induction using the fact that $v(p^k m - j) = v_p(j)$.

It follows directly from this lemma that the Newton polygon of the polynomial $\beta(1 + X) - 1$ is the following.

By the known properties of Newton's polygon it follows that there are $p - 1$ black vertices at distance $v = \frac{1}{p-1}$, $p^2 - p$ vertices at distance $\frac{1}{p(p-1)}$, etc. By considering successively the coverings $X^p, X^{p^2}, \dots$, one sees that the $p - 1$ nearest vertices are the primitive p -th roots of unity, the $p^2 - p$ following vertices are the primitive p^2 -th roots of unity, etc. The minimal model separating the vertex 1 from the other black vertices is then the following.

The calculation of the thicknesses of the blowup is done by successive differences, so for example the second thickness is the result of the calculation

$$\frac{1}{p^{k-1}(p-1)} - \frac{1}{p^{k-2}(p-1)} = \frac{1}{p^{k-1}}$$

For the other vertices ξ we can also study the polygon of $(\xi + X)^{p^k} - 1$ which will be the same given that ξ is an invertible element of $\mathcal{O}_K$, or else argue that the

multiplication by ξ produces an isomorphism from $\mathbb{C}_p$ so the distances between the vertices present the same configuration whatever the vertex considered. It follows that the minimal vertex separation model is of the form of the figure below. In this figure $p = 3$ and $\beta(X) = X^{p^3}$, ξ is a p^3 -th primitive root and ζ is a p^2 -th primitive root:

This amounts to the following induction construction:

4 Study of Belyi's coverings

We study the cover $\beta : \mathbb{P}_K^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{P}_K^1$ defined by $\beta(X) = X^a(1-X)^b$ with a and b nonzero. By the calculation of β' , there are three non-infinite ramification points: 0 of multiplicity a which we will denote O , 1 of multiplicity b which we will denote I and $\frac{a}{n}$ of multiplicity 2 which we will note C . Non-infinite critical values are 0 and $\lambda = \frac{a^a b^b}{n^n} = \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^a \left(\frac{b}{n}\right)^b$.

4.1 Tame ramifications

Here we are assuming that a , b and $n = a + b$ are coprime with p . In this case the critical value λ is invertible. So there is no reduction of black vertices on vertices O or I . Moreover the derivative $\beta' = X^{a-1}(1-X)^{b-1}(a-nX)$

has a non-zero reduction so according to the lemma 1 it suffices to study the proximity of the vertices with the central vertex C . To do this, it suffices to draw Newton's polygon of $\beta\left(\frac{a}{n} + X\right) - \lambda$. This polygon starts at abscissa 2 because $\frac{a}{n}$ is a double root of β . But we have modulo X^3

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta\left(\frac{a}{n} + X\right) - \frac{a^a b^b}{n^n} &= \left(\frac{a}{n} + X\right)^a \left(\frac{b}{n} - X\right)^b - \frac{a^a b^b}{n^n} \\
&= \left[\left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^a + a \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^{a-1} X + \frac{a(a-1)}{2} \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^{a-2} X^2 \right] \\
&\quad \left[\left(\frac{b}{n}\right)^b - b \left(\frac{b}{n}\right)^{b-1} X + \frac{b(b-1)}{2} \left(\frac{b}{n}\right)^{b-2} X^2 \right] - \frac{a^a b^b}{n^n} \\
&= X^2 \left(\frac{a^a b^{b-1} (b-1)}{n^a 2n^{b-2}} - \frac{a^a b^b}{n^{n-2}} + \frac{b^b a^{a-1} (a-1)}{n^b 2n^{a-2}} \right) \\
&= \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^{a-1} \left(\frac{b}{n}\right)^{b-1} \frac{X^2}{2} (a(b-1) - 2ab + b(a-1)) \\
&= -n \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^{a-1} \left(\frac{b}{n}\right)^{b-1} \frac{X^2}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

As the first nonzero coefficient of this polynomial is invertible then Newton's polygon is flat so all vertices are invertible: this covering has a good reduction in this model.

4.2 Bad reduction at O

We assume in this section that $v(a) \neq v(b)$. By eventually composing with $X \mapsto 1 - X$, we can assume that $v(a) > v(b)$. In this case the degree of β , $n = a + b$ has for valuation the valuation of b , the nonzero critical value $\lambda = \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^a \left(\frac{b}{n}\right)^b$ has for valuation $a(v(a) - v(b))$ and the Newton polygon of $\beta(X) - \lambda$ shows that there are a vertices of β reducing to the ramified vertex O with a valuation of $v(a) - v(b)$. Among the vertices reducing on O there is the vertex C with coordinate $\frac{a}{n}$. We proceed in the same way with the ramified vertex I by drawing the Newton polygon of the polynomial $\beta(1 + X) - \lambda$, which gives b vertices of valuation $\frac{a}{b}(v(a) - v(b))$.

Newton polygon of $\beta(X) - \lambda$

Newton polygon of $\beta(1 + X) - \lambda$

4.2.1 Study of proximities from the vertex C

For the blowup at O we study the covering on this branch via the model

$$\gamma(X) = \beta \left(\frac{a}{n} X \right) \frac{n^n}{a^a b^b} = X^a \left(\frac{n}{b} - \frac{a}{b} X \right)^b$$

We could have taken $\left(\frac{n}{a}\right)^a$ as an external factor but the chosen coefficient (which has the same valuation given that $v(b) = v(n)$) will have the advantage of being the same for the next cases. In this model the central ramified point C is placed at 1 and the corresponding critical value is 1. To study the proximity of the other vertices with C we study the Newton polygon of

$$\varphi = \gamma(1+X) - 1 = (1+X)^a \left(1 - \frac{a}{b} X \right)^b - 1$$

The first two coefficients of this polynomial are zero since the vertex C has multiplicity 2. Let us calculate the first non-zero coefficient,

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi &= \left(1 + aX + \frac{a(a-1)}{2} X^2 + \dots \right) \left(1 - aX + \frac{b(b-1)}{2} \frac{a^2}{b^2} X^2 + \dots \right) - 1 \\ &= X^2 \left(\frac{a(a-1)}{2} - a^2 + \frac{b(b-1)}{2} \frac{a^2}{b^2} \right) + \dots = -\frac{an}{2b} X^2 + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Thus the first point of Newton's polygon is at height $v(a)$. To determine the next points we will need the lemma below.

Lemma 3. *For any natural number q and any **nonzero** natural number r , for any integer m prime to p , for any polynomials E and G with coefficients in $\mathcal{O}_K$,*

$$(E + p^r G)^{p^q m} \equiv E^{p^q m} \pmod{p^{r+q}}$$

Proof. Let R_q denote the above statement at rank q . The statement is obviously true at rank 0. At rank 1 by noting u any unit of $\mathcal{O}_K$ and by using lemma 2

$$\begin{aligned} (E + p^r G)^{p^m} &= E^{p^m} + pE^{p^m-1} p^r G + puE^{p^m-2} (p^r G)^2 + \dots \\ &\quad + uE^{p^m-p} (p^r G)^p + uE^{p^m-2p} (p^r G)^{2p} + \dots + u(p^r G)^{p^m} \end{aligned}$$

the powers of p present in the last terms are $p^{pr}, p^{2pr}, \dots, p^{mpr}$, where $pr \geq r+1$ as soon as $r \geq 1$. Thus $(E + p^r G)^{p^m} = E^{p^m}$ modulo p^{r+1} . Assuming the statements proved up to the rank q ,

$$\begin{aligned} (E + p^r G)^{p^{q+1}m} &= \left((E + p^r G)^{p^q} \right)^{p^m} \\ &= \left(E^{p^q} + p^{r+q} H \right)^{p^m} \text{ d'après } (R_q) \\ &= E^{p^{q+1}m} \text{ modulo } p^{r+q+1} \text{ d'après } (R_1) \end{aligned}$$

□

We can use this result to establish that $\left(1 - \frac{a}{b} X\right)^b \equiv 1$ modulo $p^{v(a/b)+v(b)}$. We deduce that $\varphi \equiv (1+X)^a - 1$ modulo $p^{v(a)}$. This is sufficient to study its Newton polygon because we have seen that the first point has height $v(a)$.

Reasoning as in section 2 and denoting $k = v(a)$ we obtain the following Newton polygon for φ :

The valuations of the vertices are therefore of the type $\frac{1}{p^a - p^{a-1}} = \frac{1}{p-1} \frac{1}{p^{a-1}}$ for $q \geq 2$ and $\frac{1}{p-2}$ for the largest valuation. The thicknesses of the blow-up are therefore $\frac{1}{p-1} \frac{1}{p^{k-1}}$ for the first blowup then for the second

$$\frac{1}{p-1} \left(\frac{1}{p^{k-2}} - \frac{1}{p^{k-1}} \right) = \frac{1}{p^{k-1}}$$

And so on. Finally, the last blowup has the thickness

$$\frac{1}{p-2} - \frac{1}{p^2 - p} = \frac{(p-1)^2 + 1}{p(p-1)(p-2)}$$

4.2.2 Study of proximities from an unramified vertex

We then need to study the proximity of the vertices of the fiber $\beta^{-1}(\lambda)$ between them. One can always reduce to studying the vertices s initially close to O , by eventually composing with $X \mapsto 1 - X$ and assuming that $v(b) > v(a)$ for the vertices initially close to I . We can thus always assume that the considered vertex is close to O : either $v(a) > v(b)$ and C is also in the branch, or $v(b) > v(a)$ in which case $C = \frac{a}{n}$ is invertible and is close to I (because $\frac{a}{n} = 1 - \frac{b}{n}$). In all the cases one will place oneself in a model resulting from the blowup at O of thickness $v(s)$:

$$\gamma(X) = \beta(sX)\lambda^{-1}$$

By noticing that $\lambda = \beta(s) = s^a(1-s)^b$ we get

$$\gamma(X) = X^a \left(\frac{1}{1-s} - \frac{s}{1-s} X \right)^b$$

The study of the proximity of the other vertices to s is then done by observing the Newton polygon of

$$\gamma(1+X) - 1 = (1+X)^a \left(1 - \frac{s}{1-s} X \right)^b - 1$$

As s is now an antecedent of 1 then this polynomial has no constant coefficient. In order to determine the coefficient of X we can use Taylor's formula. We therefore calculate the derivative,

$$\gamma'(1) = \lambda^{-1} s^a (1-s)^{b-1} (a-ns) = \frac{a-ns}{1-s}$$

Let us first deal with the case where $v(a) > v(b)$ ie when s is close to O . In this case by noticing that $a-ns = a(1-\frac{n}{a}s)$ and that $v(1-\frac{n}{a}s)$ is the p -adic distance from s to the central vertex in the model $\beta(\frac{a}{n}X)\lambda^{-1}$ (which is equivalent on $\mathcal{O}_K$ to γ),

$$v(\gamma'(1)) = v(a) + v\left(1 - \frac{n}{a}s\right)$$

The first point of the polygon is therefore $(1, v(a) + v(1 - \frac{n}{a}s))$. To find the second point we are going to use the following lemma, which we prove without difficulty by resuming the proof of lemma 1.

Lemma 4. *If a covering model γ satisfies $\bar{\gamma}' = 0$ then the vertices reduce by subset $\{x_i\}$ satisfying $\sum_i e_i = 0 \pmod p$.*

Thus the second point has at least for abscissa p . We easily find the ordinate of this point and the following by using Lemma 3 which tells us that

$$\left(1 - \frac{s}{1-s}X\right)^b = 1^b = 1 \pmod{p^{v(\frac{s}{1-s})+v(b)} = p^{v(a)}}$$

Thus $\gamma(1+X) - 1 = (1+X)^a - 1 \pmod{p^{v(a)}}$. Using Lemma 2 we can deduce Newton's polygon:

We therefore obtain the following minimal model for the branch resulting from the blowup at O :

where $\mathcal{R}'_k$ is of the same shape as $\mathcal{R}_k$ but with terminal thicknesses for the component containing the vertex s equals to

$$\frac{v\left(1 - \frac{n}{a}s\right) + 1}{p-1} - \frac{1}{p(p-1)} = \begin{cases} \frac{(p-1)^2 + 1}{p(p-1)(p-2)} & \text{if } v(s) = \frac{1}{p-2} \\ \frac{p^{q-1}(p-1)^2 + 1}{p^q(p-1)^2} & \text{if } v(s) = \frac{1}{p^{q-1}(p-1)} \end{cases}$$

Let us now deal with the case $v(a) < v(b)$. We still consider the same model $\gamma(X) = \beta(sX)\lambda^{-1}$ and we observe the Newton polygon of $\gamma(1+X) - 1$. In this case

$$\gamma'(1) = \frac{a - ns}{1 - s} = n \frac{\frac{a}{n} - s}{1 - s}$$

Therefore $v(\gamma'(1)) = v(n) = v(a)$ so the first point of Newton's polygon has coordinates $(1, v(a))$. The rest of the reasoning is the same and leads to the same Newton's polygon. It follows that the minimal model of the vertices for the branch resulting from the blowup at O presents the same configuration as that of the covering $X \mapsto X^a$.

4.3 Bad reduction at infinity

Here we are assuming that $v(a) = v(b) < v(n)$. We are noting $r = v(a) = v(b)$ and $k = v(n)$. We proceed as in the previous case by inspecting the Newton polygons of $\beta(X) - \lambda$ and $\beta(1+X) - \lambda$. Recall that $\lambda = \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^a \left(\frac{b}{n}\right)^b$ so in this case its valuation is equal to

$$a(r - k) + b(r - k) = n(r - k)$$

It follows by drawing the two aforementioned Newton polygons that there is no vertex reducing on O nor I but that the n vertices (other than O and I) reduce on the ramified vertex ∞ . Moreover, we note that the proximity in terms of valuation is $k - r$.

It will therefore be necessary to proceed with the blowup in the neighborhood of ∞ of thickness $k - r$ to separate the black vertices from the vertex ∞ .

4.3.1 Separation of vertices from the vertex C

To do this we have once again the element $\frac{a}{n}$ which is precisely of this valuation. On the new branch the model is

$$\gamma(X) = \beta\left(\frac{a}{n}X\right) \frac{n^n}{a^a b^b} = X^a \left(\frac{n}{b} - \frac{a}{b}X\right)^b$$

The expression of γ is the same as for the previous case. It follows that the study in the neighborhood of C also gives:

$$\varphi(X) = \gamma(1+X) - 1 = (1+X)^a \left(1 - \frac{a}{b}X\right)^b - 1$$

This time the coefficient $\frac{a}{b}$ has zero valuation and we cannot therefore directly apply the lemma 3. On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} \left(1 - \frac{a}{b}X\right)^b &= \left(\frac{n}{b} - \frac{a}{b} - \frac{a}{b}X\right)^b \\ &\equiv \left(-\frac{a}{b}\right)^b (1+X)^b \pmod{p^{v(\frac{a}{b})+v(b)} = p^k} \end{aligned}$$

and likewise

$$1 = 1^b = \left(\frac{n}{b} - \frac{a}{b}\right)^b \equiv \left(-\frac{a}{b}\right)^b \pmod{p^k}$$

As a result

$$\varphi(X) = \left(-\frac{a}{b}\right)^b ((1+X)^n - 1)$$

It is therefore the same type of Newton polygon as in the previous case, therefore the same type of special fiber with the same thicknesses.

4.3.2 Separation of vertices from an unbranched vertex

We proceed as in the previous section with $\gamma(X) = \beta(sX)\lambda^{-1}$ and the observation of Newton's polygon of $\gamma(1+X) - 1$ whose minimum abscissa point is given by the valuation of $\gamma'(1) = \frac{n-as}{1-s} = a\frac{1-\frac{n}{a}s}{1-s}$. But as $v(s) < v(1)$ then $v(1-s) = v(s) = v(a) - v(n)$ so the first point of the polygon is $(1, v(n) + v(1 - \frac{n}{a}s))$. We will then proceed as in the case $v(a) < v(b)$ of section 4.2.2, noting that

$$\left(1 - \frac{s}{1-s}X\right)^b = \left(\frac{1}{1-s} - \frac{s}{1-s}(1+X)\right)^b \equiv \left(\frac{-s}{1-s}\right)^b (1+X)^b \pmod{p^{v(n)}}$$

For the last equality we used lemmas 3 and $v(s) = v(b) - v(n)$. We thus have modulo $p^{v(n)}$

$$\gamma(1+X) - 1 = (1+X)^a \left(\frac{-s}{1-s}\right)^b (1+X)^b = \left(\frac{-s}{1-s}\right)^b (1+X)^n$$

therefore the reasoning of section 4.2.2 adapts to this case with $v(n)$ instead of $v(a)$. Finally the minimal model for the vertices is of the same type as in the previous case but with only a blowup at ∞ .

4.4 The critical case

In this last section we are dealing with the cases where $v(a) = v(b) = v(n)$. We are noting k these valuations. In this case the critical value λ is invertible and Newton polygons tell us that the vertices do not reduce to O , nor to I nor to infinity. They therefore all reduce to $C = \frac{a}{n}$.

4.4.1 Study of proximities from the vertex C

In this case the vertex C is invertible and we can therefore still study

$$\gamma(x) = \beta \left(\frac{a}{n} X \right) \frac{n^n}{a^a b^b} = X^a \left(\frac{n}{b} - \frac{a}{b} X \right)^b$$

then study the proximity of the vertices with $C = 1$ in this model by considering

$$\varphi(X) = \gamma(1+X) - 1 = (1+X)^a \left(1 - \frac{a}{b} X \right)^b - 1$$

Let a' and b' be coprime with p such that $a = a'p^k$ and $b = b'p^k$ then

$$(1+X)^a \left(1 - \frac{a}{b} X \right)^b = \left((1+X)^{a'} \left(1 - \frac{a'}{b'} X \right)^{b'} \right)^{p^k}$$

We can then use the results of part 4.1 according to which, by denoting u a unit of $\mathcal{O}_K$ and G a polynomial with coefficient in $\mathcal{O}_K$,

$$(1+X)^{a'} \left(1 - \frac{a'}{b'} X \right)^{b'} = 1 + X^2(u + XG(X))$$

from which, one can deduce with the valuative properties already noticed over binomial coefficients, by noting u_i units of $\mathcal{O}_K$,

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(X) &= (1 + X^2(u + XG(X)))^{p^k} - 1 \\ &= p^k X^2(u + XG(X)) + p^k (\text{integral polynomials of degree } \geq 4) \\ &\quad + p^{k-1} u_1 (X^2(u + XG(X)))^p + p^{k-1} (\text{integral polynomials of degree } \geq 4p) \\ &\quad + p^{k-2} u_2 (X^2(u + XG(X)))^{p^2} + p^{k-2} (\text{integral polynomials of degree } \geq 4p^2) \\ &\quad + \dots \\ &\quad + (X^2(u + XG(X)))^{p^k} \end{aligned}$$

We thus obtain a Newton polygon of the following type:

The successive blows-up therefore have thicknesses

$$\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{p^{k-1}}, \frac{1}{p-1}, \frac{1}{2p^{k-1}}, \frac{1}{2p^{k-2}}, \dots, \frac{1}{2p}$$

4.4.2 Study of proximities from an unramified vertex

To study the proximities to an unramified vertex the technique used in the previous cases no longer works: Indeed by setting $\gamma(X) = \beta(sX)\lambda^{-1}$ as before $\gamma(1+X) - 1 = (1+X)^a \left(1 - \frac{s}{1-s}X\right)^b - 1$ but here $\frac{s}{1-s}$ is invertible so the lemma 3 no longer applies. In this case, we will use a technique of breaking down the fiber $\beta^{-1}(\lambda)$ into several sub-fibers.

To do this, we proceed as in the previous section: we can write β in the form B^{p^k} with $B = X^a(1-X)^b$ where (forgetting the previous notation letter a , b and n) $a, b, a+b = n$ are prime to p . By setting $g = B \left(\frac{ab}{n}X + \frac{a}{n}\right)\lambda^{-1} = (1+bX)^a(1-aX)^b$ and $\gamma = g^{p^k}$ the nonzero critical value is equal to 1 and the vertex C is placed at 0. In this model the black vertices are the points of the fiber $\gamma^{-1}(1)$ that is to say $\bigcup_{\xi \text{ } p^k\text{th root of unity}} g^{-1}(\xi)$.

We therefore notice that the vertices of $g^{p^{k+1}}$ are the vertices of g^{p^k} to which we add other vertices. More precisely:

$$\left(g^{p^{k+1}}\right)^{-1}(1) = \left(\bigcup_{\zeta \text{ } p^k\text{th root of unity}} g^{-1}(\zeta)\right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{\xi \text{ } p^{k+1}\text{th primitive root}} g^{-1}(\xi)\right)$$

We can therefore construct the minimal model of the vertices by induction.

For $k = 0$ we saw that the covering B , therefore also g , has good reduction, so the vertices have good reduction. Let $s_1, \dots, s_{n-2}$ denote the unramified vertices of g .

For $k = 1$ we have

$$(g^p)^{-1}(1) = g^{-1}(1) \cup \left(\bigcup_{\zeta \text{ } p\text{th primitive root}} g^{-1}(\zeta) \right)$$

We have just seen that $g^{-1}(1)$ has good reduction. For the other fibers, as $\zeta \neq 1$ is a regular value then $g^{-1}(\zeta)$ consists of n distinct and unbranched points. In the next section we will generically analyze the $g^{-1}(\xi)$ for ξ a p^k -th root. We will then return to the study of the case $k = 1$.

4.4.3 Analysis of regular fibers

As we have just said the $g^{-1}(\xi)$ are made up of n distinct unramified points.

Proposition 1. *Among the vertices of $g^{-1}(\xi)$ there are 2 point close to the ramified vertex C at a valuative distance of $\frac{v(1-\xi)}{2}$, which we will denote by δ^ξ and δ'^ξ . The other vertices are each close to one of the unramified vertices s_i of $g^{-1}(1)$ at a valuative distance of $v(1-\xi)$, we will note them $\sigma_1^\xi, \dots, \sigma_{n-2}^\xi$ (most of the time we will omit the indication of the base ξ)*

Proof. There are 2 vertices close to the vertex C because $g(X) - \xi = g(X) - 1 + 1 - \xi$ so its Newton polygon is the following,

For the other vertices of the fiber $g^{-1}(\xi)$ we observe the Newton polygon of $g(s + X) - \xi$ where s is one of the unramified vertices of $g^{-1}(1)$. The reasoning about polygons is then exactly the same:

□

Let us now study the proximity of the vertices of the fiber $g^{-1}(\xi)$ between them.

Proposition 2. *In the fibers $g^{-1}(\xi) = \{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_{n-2}, \delta, \delta'\}$, the vertices σ_i are at zero valuative distance and the vertices δ and δ' are at distance $\frac{v(1-\xi)}{2}$. In other words they are as far apart as possible.*

Proof. We start with proximities to an unramified vertex σ . To do this, we observe the Newton polygon of $g(\sigma + X) - \xi = g'(\sigma)X + \dots$. Moreover with $g(x) = (1 + bX)^a(1 - aX)^b$ we have $g'(X) = -nab(1 + bX)^{a-1}(1 - aX)^{b-1}X$ therefore as ξ does not reduce to 0 then $v(1 + b\sigma) = v(1 - a\sigma) = 0$ therefore $v(g'(\sigma)) = v(\sigma)$. So as σ is not close to C then this polygon is flat so σ is not close to any other vertex of the fiber $g^{-1}(\xi)$.

Let us then study the proximities of the vertices of the fiber to a vertex δ close to C . As before we consider the Newton polygon $g(\delta + X) - \xi$. From what we have seen above the proximity of δ with C is $\frac{v(1-\xi)}{2}$ therefore $v(g'(\delta)) = \frac{v(1-\xi)}{2}$ which gives a first point of the polygon with coordinates $(1, \frac{v(1-\xi)}{2})$. There is thus at least one point of the fiber $g^{-1}(\xi)$ close to δ which we already knew given that δ and δ' are both close to C . We also know that there are no other vertices of the fiber close to δ from the previous reasoning on σ . Thus the second point of the polygon is necessarily $(2, 0)$.

It follows that the distance between the two vertices δ and δ' is $\frac{v(1-\xi)}{2}$. $\square$

The following proposition states the distances between two fibers $g^{-1}(\xi)$ and $g^{-1}(\tilde{\xi})$.

Proposition 3. *The proximities between the fibers $g^{-1}(\xi)$ and $g^{-1}(\tilde{\xi})$ are summarized in the following diagram,*

According to section 2, case 2 occurs when ξ and $\tilde{\xi}$ are two p^q -th primitive roots, and in this case $v(1 - \xi) = v(1 - \tilde{\xi})$. In case 1 we will have $v(\xi - \tilde{\xi}) = \min(v(1 - \xi), v(1 - \tilde{\xi}))$.

Proof. If $\sigma \in g^{-1}(\xi)$ then the given distance follows from the equality $g(\sigma + X) - \tilde{\xi} = g(\sigma + X) - \xi + \xi - \tilde{\xi}$ and from the observation of the corresponding Newton polygon

If $\delta \in g^{-1}(\xi)$ we also observe the Newton polygon of $g(\delta + X) - \tilde{\xi} = g(\delta + X) - \xi + \xi - \tilde{\xi}$ and we see the two scenarios emerge.

□

4.4.4 End of the study of proximities in the case $k = 1$

Let us resume the study of

$$(g^p)^{-1}(1) = g^{-1}(1) \cup \left(\bigcup_{\zeta \text{ } p\text{-th root of unity}} g^{-1}(\zeta) \right)$$

We have from the previous section

- A good reduction fiber $g^{-1}(1) = \{s_1, \dots, x_{n-2}, C\}$
- $p - 1$ fibers $g^{-1}(\zeta^i) = \{\sigma_1^i, \dots, \sigma_{n-2}^i, \delta^i, \delta'^i\}$

which have the following proximities,

So we have the following minimal model

We denoted $\mathcal{S}_1$ and $\mathcal{R}_1$ the patterns of this model in order to initiate a recurrence, $\mathcal{R}_1$ being the same pattern as its namesake from section 2.

4.4.5 Model in case $k = 2$

We have in this case

$$(g^{p^2})^{-1}(1) = (g^p)^{-1}(1) \cup \left(\bigcup_{\zeta \text{ } p\text{-th primitive root}} (g^p)^{-1}(\zeta) \right)$$

The branches containing the vertices s_i are easy to determine because for each p^2 -th root of unity, the fiber $g^{-1}(\xi)$ has a vertex σ_i close to s_i and the distances in this branch are given by $v(\xi - \widetilde{\xi})$ so these branches are in fact isomorphic to the minimal model of the vertices of the cover X^{p^2} or in general X^{p^k} . The only branch of the vertices close to C remains to be elucidated. Let S_2 denote the set of these vertices. We then have

$$S_2 = S_1 \cup \bigcup_{i=1}^{p-1} S_1^i$$

where $S_1 = \{C, \delta^\zeta, \delta'^\zeta\}_{\zeta \text{ primitive } p\text{-th root}}$ and for all i between 1 and $p-1$, denoting ξ a p^2 -th primitive root,

$$S_1^i = \{\delta^{\xi^i}, \delta'^{\xi^i}, \delta^{\zeta\xi^i}, \delta'^{\zeta\xi^i}, \dots, \delta^{\zeta^{p-1}\xi^i}, \delta'^{\zeta^{p-1}\xi^i}\}$$

where ξ is a p^2 -th root of unity. For example for S_1^2 ,

Grouping of primitive roots in the case $p = 7$

With index i, j fixed, it follows from section 3 and proposition 2 that the vertices $\delta^{\zeta^j\xi^i}$ and $\delta'^{\zeta^j\xi^i}$ are at distance $\frac{1}{2p(p-1)}$ between them.

For j varying between 1 and $p-1$, according to proposition 3 and section 3 the vertices $\delta^{\zeta^j\xi}$ are at distance $\frac{1}{p-1} - \frac{1}{2p(p-1)} > \frac{1}{2p(p-1)}$.

The minimal model for S_1^i therefore presents a first blowup of thickness $\frac{1}{2p(p-1)}$ around δ and δ' . There is then a second blowup around δ and another around δ' which has the same thickness of $\left(\frac{1}{p-1} - \frac{1}{2p(p-1)}\right) - \frac{1}{2p(p-1)} = \frac{1}{p}$.

Similarly the vertices of S_1 are all at distance $\frac{1}{2(p-1)}$ between them, C is at distance $\frac{1}{2p(p-1)}$ from the vertices of S_1^i and the unramified vertices δ of S_1 are all at distance $\frac{1}{2p(p-1)}$ from the vertices of S_1^i . The same is true between the vertices of S_1^i and S_1^j which are at a distance from $\frac{1}{2p(p-1)}$. The minimal vertex separation model of S_2 is therefore the following:

We therefore see the following induction construction

4.4.6 General construction

In general, by denoting S_k the branch of the minimal vertex model of g^{p^k} containing the ramified vertex C , we have

$$S_k = S_{k-1} \cup \bigcup_{i=1}^{p-1} S_{k-1}^i$$

where the S_{k-1}^i are the groupings of the $\{\delta^{\zeta^j \xi^i} \delta'^{\zeta^j \xi^i}\}_j$ with ξ a p^k -th primitive root and ζ a p^{k-1} -th primitive root.

The same phenomenon then occurs as for the case $k = 2$: the S_{k-1}^i presents two branches of the type $\mathcal{R}_{k-1}$ which are at a distance $\frac{1}{2p^{k-2}(p-1)}$ between them as

well as the branches S_{k-1}^i , S_{k-1}^j and S_{k-1} between them. We therefore obtain the model of S_k by induction in the following way.

References

- [1] Leonardo Zapponi. “Specialization of polynomial covers of prime degree”. In: *Pacific Journal of Mathematics* 214.1 (2004), pp. 161–183.